

ASSESSING GENERATION BERENCANA' AMBASSADOR ENGAGEMENT TOWARDS THEIR ROLE AS CHANGE AGENTS FOR INDONESIA'S YOUTH RESILIENCE INITIATIVE - A BRAND RESONANCE PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

The National Family Planning Coordinating Board of Indonesia (BKKBN) launched the Generation Berencana (GenRe) as a youth resilience program in response to adolescent issues. The GenRe Ambassadors (GA) are expected to be role models by becoming change agents whose job is to socialize and persuade young people in Indonesia to behave in a healthy manner. The success of carrying out the role of ambassador is determined, among other things, by the extent of engagement formed between the ambassador and the program for which he is responsible. Therefore, the aim of this research is to analyze the GA's engagement towards GenRe by adapting the concept of brand resonance pyramid. This research approach is qualitative and employs phenomenological methods. The informants are the GA, who have served as ambassadors for 2–3 years. Sampling was carried out using a snowball technique for further in-depth interviews. The result of this study is that GA's level of engagement with GenRe has actually reached the highest phase, resonance, but it has not yet formed an attitude of engagement because of GA's objections to having to spend personal funds to finance GenRe activities. Considering the good performance of GA, it should be the concern of BKKBN to immediately respond to GA's dissatisfaction.

Keywords: Change Agents, Brand Resonance Pyramid, Engagement, GenRe, Ambassadors

INTRODUCTION

One of the most essential aspects determining a country's success is the quality of its human resources. Based on the most recent demographic data, adolescents represent the majority of the population structure in Indonesia, followed by children and the elderly. According to the 2020 National Socio-Economic Survey (Susenas), an estimated 64.50 million Indonesians are in the youth age group [1]. This indicates that Indonesia will benefit from a population bonus

over the next 1-3 decades as the younger generation enters the productive age group. This momentum must be carefully planned in order to capitalize on these prospects.

As a consequence, the Indonesian government must implement substantial initiatives to prepare the quality of its human resources in order to face global competitive workforce. However, it is obvious that throughout the transition from youth to adulthood, adolescents frequently encounter complex issues such as premarital sex, early marriage, and drug usage. Adolescents, especially in today's digital age, have relatively easy access to information, both positive and negative information that might influence their attitudes and behavior.

As a step to respond to the adolescent's issues, the National Family Planning Coordinating Board of Indonesia (BKKBN) as an institution which is responsible in managing population and family planning in Indonesia need to pay attention in terms of bringing adolescents into a well-planned and prosperous adulthood. Therefore, since the year of 2014, the BKKBN launched the *Generasi Berencana* or GenRe as a youth resilience program. GenRe was developed to build healthy, intelligent and responsible youth, towards themselves, their families, and the community [2]. The key messages and the symbol of GenRe that embedded through all campaign activities are; say no to pre-marital sex, say no to early marriage and say no to drug addiction. The target audience is adolescents, within the age of 12 until 22 years old and have never been married.

The BKKBN also formed the *Genre Indonesia* which functions as a forum for the development and capability of youth who join the GenRe program. Through this forum the selection of GenRe Ambassadors is carried out. The selection of Genre Ambassadors is held annually in 34 provinces in Indonesia and the participants who participate are teenagers aged 17-22 years. All activities and responsibilities of Genre Ambassadors will be fostered and supervised by the BKKBN. GA is a change agent whose job is to socialize and persuade young people in Indonesia to behave in a healthy manner by avoiding pre-marital sex, early marriage and drug use. GA is also expected to be a role model for Indonesian youth who are serious about preparing for the future.

Youth as a Change Agent

Studies about change agents and the facilitator role mostly describe sets of skills and personal qualities. The change agent is not just a passive recipient of a role; they are playing an active part in determining their own role behavior. Therefore, understanding how the roles of change agents are created in healthcare organizations is of significance [3] [4].

Change agent are a well-recognized aspect of communication theory, and although they may not be discussed as such, they are an integral part of many public information campaigns [5]. As Rogers [6] stated that one main role of the change agent is to facilitate the flow of innovations from a change agency to an audience of clients. This implies that the change agent's communication approach must be tailored to the demands of the intended audience in order to ensure that innovation flows as expected.

Change agents can be internal (e.g., organizational executives who support change or organizational "opinion leaders" who implicitly encourage change through their endorsement) and external agent. As stated by Alagoz et al. [7] External change agents defined as: "Individuals who are affiliated with an outside entity who formally influence or facilitate intervention decisions in a desirable direction. Since GA are external agent, this paper focuses on the function of GA as external change agent. Conduct educational outreach visits, ongoing training and external facilitation, all of which are examples of implementation strategies where external change agents play an essential role [8].

Previous research related to adolescents as change agents has been discussed a lot in the context of the character of adolescents who become change agents, the appropriate change agent selection method, the provision of materials needed by adolescents as change agents, and evaluating the effectiveness of adolescents in carrying out their roles as change agents [9] [10] [11] [12].

The Study of Pavarini et al., [10] On mental health and well-being (MHWB) underlines the significance of youth as active agents in the implementation of MHBW initiatives in low- and middle-income nations. This study assessed young people's engagement intentions, areas of influence, capacity building needs, and major participation constraints. Participants in this study considered schools and community settings to be the most significant platforms for engagement. The biggest reported barrier to participation was a lack of knowledge about mental health, and mental health workshops were the primary training need. Therefore, the involvement of policymakers or young service providers that manage MHWB must equip youth change agents with relevant knowledge and skills.

Using Theory of Planned Behavior, Williford et al., [11] Evaluated the behavioral intentions of peer leaders as change agents in a suicide prevention program. Behavioral intention refers to the desire or interest to undertake specific activities, which signifies someone's willingness to perform the behavior. The results of this study indicate that certain internal characteristics, including extra-version, optimism, kindness, and empathy, can strengthen the behavioral intention to be involved as change agents in a suicide prevention program.

While Pickering et al., [12] study's also emphasizes the significance of peer leaders as change agents in the context of preventing adolescent suicide which peer persuasion is thought to be more effective. This study looked at the possibility of diffusion programs being more effective if peer leaders had been selected using network-informed selection techniques. The proposed theoretical alternate peer leader sets based on social network characteristics are: opinion leadership, centrality metrics, and key players.

The study by Chandraratne et al.[9] examines the effectiveness of a community-based youth-targeted education program in Colombo, Sri Lanka. Facilitators trained youth club members aged 15–29 to identify cardiovascular disease risk factors and take action to address pertinent issues in their communities. Employing youths as change agents was beneficial in reducing body weight among young adults in Sri Lanka, according to the findings of this study.

Given the importance of the role of change agents, it is essential to gain a deeper understanding of their experiences. In contrast to prior research and in order to expand the study of adolescents as change agents, the researcher attempts to examine how GA perceive their responsibilities and the engagement they form with the GenRe Program as change agents. Unfortunately, very little research has been devoted to the role of GA. The previous research on GenRe discussed more about other aspects of implementing GenRe programs.

However, several research regarding GenRe have been conducted. A research using diffusion of innovation theory to analyze the adoption process of GenRe had been done in Pekanbaru, Riau [13]. This study found that the diffusion process innovation GenRe in Pekanbaru, Riau has been done well, if analyzing from the perspective of the basic elements of innovation diffusion, i.e. innovation, communication channel, time period and members of social system. Likewise with the stages of adoption i.e. the stage of knowledge, persuasion, decision making, implementation, until the stabilization phase has been passed smoothly by adolescents [13].

Another study conducted to description of Generasi Berencana Program (GenRe) in Indonesia and East Java Province). This study focused on the increasing age of first marriage, adolescent reproductive health, family development program for adolescent and Counselling Information Centers for Youth in East Java. This study found that GenRe which covers three indicators in both Indonesia and East Java is less optimally implemented. GenRe was not successful in preventing adolescent from getting married early since adolescents was not interested and tend to ignored message conveyed by Genre. This study suggest to increase the knowledge and exposure of three indicators of the GenRe for adolescents through families [14].

Meanwhile, study of effectiveness on GenRe community among high school students in Banda Aceh shown that the messages of GenRe i.e. pre-marital sex, early marriage and drugs addiction perceived effectively only among the students who are member of PIK (GenRe community) and on the contrary ignored by students who are not a member of GenRe community. Furthermore the students who are member of GenRe community tend to be more enthusiastic in searching an information regarding reproduction health by attending socialization and training related to adolescent reproductive health [15].

Elected GA serve as change agents whose mission it is to socialize and encourage adolescents to avoid premarital sex, early marriage, and drug use, as well as to invite youth to participate in beneficial activities. These responsibilities would be completed successfully if GA are enthusiastic in the work they accomplish. The GA should be proud to act as role models for young Indonesians, who are essential to the nation's growth. When the GA has a satisfying experience while serving their task, a sense of pride will arise. In this study, the engagement that has built between GA and the duties for which they are responsible will be investigated in this study from a branding perspective, focusing on Keller's concept of pyramid brand resonance [16].

Health Branding

Although branding traditionally has been associated with products and services, branding principles utilization are relevant to other entities such as people, places ideas including health

campaigns [16]. In line with the complexity of health issues nowadays including issues that focus of GenRe, a more sophisticated health communication strategy is required. There is a visible trend in public health literature, which emphasizes the need to communicate public health from branding perspective. Health branding is commonly seen as a form of public trust toward the health information given by the health practitioners.

As Basu & Wang [17] stated, health branding focuses on educating as well as building audience engagement and relationships instead of one sided educating and instructing. As a brand, communicated healthy behavior will resonate and create stickiness and ensure long term relationship and along a way provide audience act as an agents of change. Unfortunately little effort has been made to brand the campaign and use branding strategies to communicate value and forge long-term relationships with the target audience. Correspondingly, up to now, there are very few scientific articles on branding and public health campaigns. However, A various study regarding health branding had been done as follows; Act-Belong-Commit (ABC) mental health campaign that associates messages of the campaign with an aboriginal indigenous culture strategy, successfully conducted in order to increase social and emotional well-being among an Aboriginal Community [18]. Another study is about social branding. This study evaluated a Social Branding intervention, CRUSH, which included an aspirational brand, social events, and targeted media to discourage smoking among LGBT young adults in Las Vegas, NV. The initiator of the campaign focus on psychographics factor, which can associate with self-concept, interests, and lifestyle. The brand describes its promoted lifestyle as “cute, fresh, and smoke free.” The Social Brand identity was communicated throughout the campaign, which integrated several elements including branded events with live performances, DJs, dancers, and models [19].

One health campaigns are considered successful using the health branding approach and are widely discussed in academic literature are VERB campaigns. The VERB campaign was launched in 2002 by the Department of Health and Human Services (HHS) and the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) and developed to increase physical activity levels among children 9 to 13 years of age (“tweens”). Messages were designed to empower tweens to become more physically active by communicating benefits unique to different segments of the audience (i.e., fun for younger children, accessibility for children from families in lower socioeconomic levels, increased sociability for girls) [20] The campaign encouraged tweens to be more physically active and associated it as cool part of all tweens’ lives. This message was embodied by the tag line “VERB: It’s what you do. The campaign applies similar marketing strategies and tactics that brands like Nike or Nickelodeon use to create cool, fun relationships with its audience. The strategy to associating the VERB and the target audience is done by involving them in planning physical activities they enjoy the most.

Brand Resonance

The branding concept used in this study is brand resonance. As stated by Keller [16] Brand Resonance refers to the relationship a consumer or audience has with the product and how well they relate to the brand the brand resonance model views the process of creating a brand as a series of steps, each of which depends on the previous step's success in fulfilling its goals. The

steps consist of brand salience as the first step. Followed by brand performance and brand imagery as the second step. The third step are brand judgement and brand feeling. The final step is resonance, which includes four stages: behavioral loyalty, attitude attachment, a sense of community, and active engagement. The justification of each stage in the Brand Resonance Pyramid according to Keller is as follows;

Adapting the Brand Resonance Pyramid to Illustrate the GenRe's Ambassador Engagement

The Salience stage is the first encounter between the customer and the brand. Salience assesses many faces of brand awareness as well as how frequently and easily the brand is recognized and recalled in various contexts. This is reflected in the quantity (how much) and quality (how fresh and relevant) the brand information network is in memory, or “share thoughts” brand. It also ensures that customers know which of their “needs” the brand through these products is designed to satisfy. In other words, awareness of the presence of a brand is easy to form as long as the brand is in accordance with the needs of the customer. Awareness is related with creating the positive perception of a brand in the consumer's mind and of achieving brand knowledge that make a positive as well as comprehensive awareness about a brand [21].

When customers become aware of a brand, it is likely that they will be interested in learning more about its performance and image. At the Performance stage, the audience evaluates the extent to which customers' functional needs are addressed. The customer considers elements such as the brand's quality, its reliability, and its affordability. While brand imagery is the customer's evaluation of the brand's non-functional aspects. Imagery refers to a customer's mental image of a brand. This element affects the customer's perception of the brand user's image and the image that will be generated of him if he uses the brand.

The subsequent phase is Judgments and Feeling. This stage is developed when the consumer decides to purchase the brand. After gaining experience with a brand as a user, a customer will form his or her own opinions and evaluations regarding the brand. Customers may form a variety of opinions regarding a brand, but four are particularly significant: opinions regarding quality, credibility, consideration, and superiority.

While Feeling stage refers to how customers feel about the brand or how emotionally attached they are to it. How does the brand influence the self-perception and interpersonal relationships with others. These emotions may be subtle or severe, joyful or negative. The customer can build feelings for the brand in terms of enjoyment, security, self-respect, and social acceptance.

Resonance, the most advanced stage, is where customer engagement has been established. Vivek et al. [22] Also proposed that value, trust, loyalty, word of mouth/advocacy, affective commitment, brand community, and involvement are potential consequences of customer engagement. The goal is to build a solid connection and foster brand attachment. According to Keller [16], this stage consists of four phases: Behavioral Loyalty, Attitudinal Attachment, Sense of Community and Active Involvement. Behavioral loyalty refers to how frequently and how much they spend on a brand. Further, customers who have a strong Attitudinal Attachment with a brand may claim to adore it or to count it among their most valued things. The

subsequent phase is a Sense of Community, which happens when consumers feel a sense of community with other brand enthusiasts. Communities can form around brand-loyal consumers who share their attachment, affection, and sense of belonging [23]. This customer is enthusiastic about starting a community or joining the community of the brand they loves. Finally, their willingness to devote time, effort, money, or other resources to a brand above and beyond what is required likely the strongest indication of brand engagement. This customer and brand managers may gather to discuss and share ideas for brand development.

In this study, the brand resonance pyramid was modified to examine to understand the extent to which GenRe Ambassadors are attached to the GenRe program. The following is a description of the application of the brand resonance model in the context of the Genre Ambassador: The Salience stage in the context of GenRe is the initial stage when adolescents recognize GenRe content on social media and events held at school or elsewhere. BKKBN as the organizer of GenRe, targets youth who are interested in developing their own capacity and benefiting other youth. GA's regular activities are shown on Instagram and TikTok and talk shows about premarital sex, early marriage and drug use are BKKBN's efforts to persuade teenagers to be interested in GenRe programs.

If they decide to pursue their curiosity, they will learn more about GenRe performance (Performance stage) and determine whether GenRe programs can serve as a means of achieving self-actualization. Moreover, the opportunity to become a GenRe Ambassador is a main attraction. They also compared it to similar youth programs held by other organizations. Apart from looking at the functional aspect, adolescents also curious about the image of other adolescents who have become GA (Imagery Stage) and imagine if they themselves become GA. In this stage, adolescents may consider joining the GenRe community,

The next stage is judgment. At this step, adolescents have become GA and have a lot of experience being involved in GenRe activities. They evaluate whether their involvement in GenRe activities provides many functional benefits for them, such as having extensive knowledge about pre-marital sex, early marriage and drug use, having techniques for organizing events, social media content, as well as counselling techniques for peers and other functional benefits. Moreover, after serving as a representative for the GenRe for some periods, they assess how the experience affected their emotional experiences, including whether they felt more proud, appreciated by others, or confident in themselves.

Resonance, is the point at which engagement between GA and GenRe is well-established. This stage consists of four phases. The amount of time and frequency that GA devote to GenRe activities is referred to as behavioral loyalty phase. Furthermore, GA who have a close attitudinal attachment to GenRe may declare they adore it or list it among their most valuable youth activities. The third phase is a sense of community, which happens when GA identify with other individuals who are considering joining the GenRe program. By highlighting the advantages of joining the GenRe community and becoming a GenRe Ambassador, they will influence their friends to join the GenRe community. Finally, GA reaches the active involvement phase when he or she is prepared to put in the time, energy, money, or other

resources necessary to enhance the GenRe program in collaboration with the BKKBN. The figure below is an adaptation of the brand resonance pyramid to illustrate GA engagement

Fig. 1. Adaptation of The Brand Resonance Pyramid to Illustrate GA Engagement.

METHODOLOGY

This research approach is qualitative and employs phenomenological methods. Creswell [24] defined phenomenology as a method for describing the meaning of a concept or phenomena through the lived experiences of various individuals. At the heart of phenomenological research is the concept of the lifeworld, which acknowledges that each individual's reality is unique and that individual behaviors can only be comprehended through understanding the life worlds of individuals and their shared viewpoints [25]. Therefore, it is the responsibility of researchers to access individuals' "common-sense reasoning" in order to evaluate their motivations, actions, and social reality from their perspective. The phenomenon studied is the engagement of the GenRe Ambassadors' towards their roles as change agents for Indonesia's youth resilience initiatives. This method and technique allowed the GenRe Ambassador to convey their thoughts, feelings, and experiences in their own words, unrestricted by the fixed-response questions typically used in quantitative research.

The subject of this research is the GenRe Ambassador who is in charge of promoting the GenRe program to young people in Indonesia. The informants consist of five adolescents who have served as GenRe Ambassadors for 2-3 years. Sampling was carried out using a snowball sampling technique to obtain informants who fit the predetermined criteria. This sampling method involves primary data sources nominating other potential data sources who will be able to participate in research studies [25].

Furthermore, researchers used in-depth interviews to collect data from informants. The aspect that was elaborated in the in-depth interview is how the engagement of GenRe Ambassadors formed in relation to their roles as change agents for Indonesia's youth resilience initiative. In the data analysis process, the engagement formed was categorized based on the brand

resonance pyramid, i.e., salient, performance and imagery, judgment and feeling, and resonance.

RESULT

The results are explained based on the brand resonance pyramid framework so that it can be seen in depth how GA perceive their role as change agents and the extent of the attachment formed.

Fig. 2. GA's level of engagement to GenRe.

Awareness of The Existence Of The GenRe Program - GenRe Seems Suitable For Me, Who Does Not Wish to be An Ordinary Teenager.

Basically the GA who became informants in this research are adolescents who have the view that adolescence must be filled with usefulness. They really pay attention to programs that can increase their capacity as a youth people.

“As a teenager I “can't just study at school and hang out with friends. There must be extra-curricular activities that are beneficial for my self-development. Well, I happened to meet with a platform called Generasi Berencana (GenRe). As a youth , I was often eager to try various useful activities. That's why I'm searching what GA are. Oh, it turns out that GA are role models for teenagers in Indonesia. That's where I became interested, especially at my school where juvenile delinquency occurs, such as using drugs and having free sex. I am challenged to invite them to do positive things and stay away from bad behavior.” (GA 1- male, age 17)

“When GA visited my campus, I was astounded. They're really cool. The GA's values are really relatable to me because I am interested in issues of mental health and self-development for youth. Including how to resist the urge to do pre-marital sex and drug use.” (GA4 - female, age 20)

Observation and Assessment Of GenRe, Activities - Genre is Great Program compare to other youth program

Informants attempted to learn more about GenRe's actions via social media and GenRe's events. They also asked questions and observed how the GA carried out their roles as change agents. Furthermore, the key concerns of informants were information surrounding the selection of GA and tips for being selected as GA.

"Before joining the GenRe, I was frequently requested to participate in GenRe activities such as seminars, webinars, and organising youth empowerment events by friends who were members of the genre community. Compared to other programs for teens, GenRe programs are more well-planned. It is evident from routine activities such as GA elections, GenRe jamboree, workshops related to the prevention of free sex and drugs. They also mentioned that they received knowledge and abilities that would not have gotten in school, such as public speaking and event planning." (GA 2- female, age 19).

Find Out More About Genre Ambassador Profile - I Feel Useful Being Trusted as A Young Change Agent.

"The GA appeared to be very confident and smart. In any case, it's different among teens. They appear to be honored to carry the title of GenRe Ambassador. And thus I imagine that if I were to be GA, I will be proud." (GA 3 –Male, age 19).

Emotional Experience While Serving as GA - The GA are Fascinating, Becoming a GA is My Dream

The informants' interactions with friends who had previously become GA, along with the positive experiences they shared, influenced their decision to join the GenRe community. The purpose of their participation is to become GA and spread compassion to other adolescents. Despite having to go through a rigorous screening process and compete against a large number of other adolescents, the informants were able to become GA. The informant thought that being a GA was the perfect choice because there were many benefits to being a GenRe ambassador.

BKKBN provided them with modules and training on how to educate and persuade adolescents to avoid ABC. They are also urged to have a positive attitude and to carry themselves as teens who can serve as role models. Emotional qualities such as happiness, pride, and increased self-confidence are vital in making them feel linked to GenRe programs.

"I had several benefits from joining GenRe, both as a member of the GenRe community and after becoming GA." Learn to arrange events, knowledge sharing and answer questions from other teen, which makes me nervous but also proud...hehe " (GA1 - male, age 17).

"GenRe has made a significant difference in my personal development. I am no longer shy, and I am now more confident in public speaking." (GA2- female 19).

"I am honored being GA because I am trusted to be an agent of change who must have a positive vibes for teenagers. As a GA, you also must constantly be positive and set a good example for your friends. It's not easy to play a role like that since some of my friends make

fun of me, saying things like "you're a hypocrite, you're pretentious..." but I'm fine. It's a challenge for me, hehehe." (GA4- female, 20).

GA's Level of Engagement to Genre - I love being part of GenRe, yet slightly disappointed

The ultimate level of engagement is resonance, in which informants feel that they are a part of GenRe and not simply doing a task. There are 4 phases of resonance: behavioral loyalty, attitude attachment, a sense of community, and active involvement.

Behavioral Loyalty

The role of GA is quite time-consuming, so that although there are many opportunities to participate in social activities or join other youth organizations, they choose to focus on carrying out their duties as GA.

"I'm actually a person who enjoys taking part in any activities outside of school such as, basketball, being involved in social campaigns and participating in entrepreneurship workshops too, but because my busy life as a GA is quite time-consuming I decide to prioritize GenRe, if I have free time I'll join other extra curricular activities" (GA 3 – Male, age 19).

"I'm not interested in other activities. At school, there are many assignments plus being a GA, who has to be mobile to carry out counselling, everywhere. I don't think I have the energy to join other organizations, hehehe".(GA 1- Male , age 17).

Attitudinal Attachment

Informant who have a close attitudinal attachment to GenRe may declare they adore it or list it among their most valuable youth activities. They told their friends how excited they were to serve as GA with all the challenges. Benefits in the form of additional knowledge, skills, increasing self-confidence, having networking and being part of a youth program on a national scale is a matter of pride that needs to be passed on to friends.

"Our duty as GAs is to invite our colleagues to engage in GenRe activities, among other things. Of course, I'm delighted to do it because I've noticed a significant improvement in myself since being a GA. I'm more confident today, and I'm frequently requested to represent national events. I've been exposed in the media, and I meet a lot of people. That's what I explain to my peers." (GA 4 - Female, age 20).

"Most of my classmates have no idea what GenRe is. This is because, when compared to basketball games, art performances, and TikTok dances, GenRe is impressed with programming, which is serious and not entertaining. Even if I am occasionally ignored, I continue to try to get my friends to join the GenRe community. They are unaware that GenRe events are also enjoyable and not solely serious." (GA 1- Male, age 17).

Sense of Community

GA is also responsible for establishing a GenRe community, which is facilitated by the GenRe organization in partnership with schools, campuses, and the local neighborhood. Despite the

possibility of being picked as GA, it turns out that it is difficult to invite teenagers to join the genre's community. Nonetheless, they are eager to invite their friends to join the GenRe community.

“I've attempted to ask campus buddies to join a GenRe community, but many have refused. Sad indeed, yet I keep on going and maintain my spirit! They are more interested in campus-wide activities and the election of ambassadors with greater glitz and glamour. This may also inspire GenRe organizers to create more activities that emphasize the fun element. I'm enthusiastic about inviting teenage boys in my neighbourhood to join the GenRe community, not only because it's one of the assessments of my performance as a GA, but also because I want them to take part in useful activities rather than just hanging out playing cards, playing guitar, or teasing girls who passed in front of them.” (GA 3 - Male, Age 19).

Active Involvement

Although the informants are very enthusiastic and happy to carry out their duties as GA, they have not fully put the time, energy, and especially money, to enhance the GenRe program with the GenRe organizers. After all, they are students who also have to prioritize their tasks at school or campus. In addition, related to the financial aspect, what they complain about is the lack of funds provided by the BKKBN to organize activities, so they often use personal funds.

“I love being part of GenRe but I disagree to having to frequently use the earnings of GenRe community members to fund GenRe events. Moreover, if you want to arrange a fantastic event, you need a lot of money, and the GenRe organizers should support this.” (GA- Female, age 19).

“I really want to be involved in thinking about ways for developing the genre in the future. Even though I don't receive an honorarium as a GA, I don't have a problem, but if I have to spend my own money to put on an event, promotion to other regions feels heavy, doesn't it? I don't have any money because I'm a student. There are operating funding from GenRe organizers, but they are insufficient to hold a variety of activities based on the interests of today's youth, rather than simply hosting webinars with speakers who are less popular among teens.” (GA- Female, Age, 20).

“Despite the fact that there are numerous projects in my thoughts to promote GenRe and make it more accessible to young people. I want to be able to invite popular teen influencers to talk about ABC issues, hold competitions with attractive rewards, and so on, so that GenRe becomes more well-known and in demand. But sadly the funds are not enough. I mind if I have to use my own money. So we, as GA, run the existing program according to the operational funds provided.” (GA- Male, Age, 19).

DISCUSSION

The results of this study indicate that in the salient stage, what BKKBN has been doing to recruit young people who have the potential to become agents of change is able to attract attention. Adolescents who are recruited to serve as GAs are those who pursue experiences that

will enhance both their own development and the development of their peers. They exhibit characteristics of adolescents, such as high rates of exploration and novelty-seeking [26] in a positive context. The internal characteristics that a change agent must possess are extraversion, optimism, kindness, and empathy as explained in Williford et al., study [11] also found in GA. They do not wish to be ordinary adolescents who merely attend school or college and socialize with their peers. They aspire to take part in organizations that can optimize their potential as adolescents. In light of this, they consider the GenRe Program to be an ideal environment for self-actualization, knowledge acquisition, skill development, and network expansion. What BKKBN has been doing to recruit young people who have the potential to become agents of change is able to attract the attention of teenagers.

Furthermore, the content on Instagram and Tiktok that describes the process of selecting GA and GA's activities in carrying out their duties is the most appealing for them.. Adolescents who are future-focused, find particular interest in activities like talk programs with the theme of the importance of planning for the future at a young age and at the same time help peers avoiding pre-marital sex, early marriage and drug use. The performance and imagery of the previous GA with all their activities made adolescents dream of becoming the next GA. Previous GA is a role model that motivates informants to seriously carry out the selection to become GA. Role models are often seen as a way of motivating individuals to perform novel behaviors and inspire them to set ambitious goals [27].

Exposing GA activities is an effective way to attract adolescent's attention to become GenRe's change agent, because there are similarities in age, character and interests. This is in line with the findings of the study by Hyemin et al., [28] Which explains that promoting voluntary service to youth is more effective by telling stories of peers who have previously become volunteers rather than telling the success of professional change agents who have experience in providing social services. (performance and imagery stage).

Curiosity and the ideal overview of GA motivated them to join the GenRe community. When they officially joined this group, they gained a great deal of previously unacquainted experience, such as assisting senior GA in conducting roadshows to educate peers to avoid pre-marital sex, early marriage and drug use., providing peer counselling, and hosting workshops. The most challenging part for members of the GenRe community is the selection process to become a GA, in which they must compete other GenRe members from throughout Indonesia. The stages of the selection process include a written test of general knowledge, presentation on the topic of youth issues and an interview about motivation to become a GA.

Therefore, when they were finally elected as GA, they felt a sense of pride and were compelled to take their duty seriously. During their experience as GAs, they judged the GenRe program to be an excellent and necessary resource for youth. As an adolescent, GA also feels proud, more confident, and valued. GAs typically possess a high self-esteem. Self-esteem is the evaluation of a person's thoughts and attitudes regarding his or her own capabilities and ideals [29]. Adolescents with high levels of self-esteem frequently have great self-experiences and better interpersonal communication, and greater physical and mental health [30] [31]. There is a reciprocal relationship between GA's self-esteem and the motivation to act as a change agent.

Those GA with a strong sense of self-esteem will perform their responsibilities competently. Consequently, GA's self-esteem is enhanced as a result of their successful performance of assigned tasks and the recognition they receive from GenRe organizers and peers. They believed that joining the GenRe program was the best decision. Even willing to put aside other extracurricular interests in order to concentrate exclusively on the GenRe program on addition of their academic obligations.

Referring to the brand resonance stage [16], GAs have reached the engagement stage, where they are loyal and feel that they are the face of GenRe which represents the ideal Indonesian youth. The resonance stage is the stage where the intensity, or the depth of the psychological bond that customers have with the brand is formed, as well as the level of activity engendered by this loyalty. Seriousness and pride in playing the role of change agent for the GenRe program gradually increase engagement and loyalty. Referring to the resonance stage, GA has reached the sense of community phase. Belonging to a community in which individuals feel linked, supported, and important is a "basic human phenomena of collective experience" [32] [33]. Positive experiences as GA and part of the GenRe community make GA not only serious in carrying out their duties but are also passionate about inviting their peers to join the GenRe community, forming a new GenRe community at their school or campus, and persuading their peers to become the next GA.

Even though it seemed so perfect to be a GA, when this interview was elaborated more deeply, it turned out that there was also a hint of disappointment related to the lack of operational funds provided, while the program had to be run. Often, they are forced to fund their own events that should be funded by the BKKBN.

According to GA, the bureaucracy to obtain operational funds is complicated, which leads to no funds being provided. As a result, several programs that have been planned cannot be executed. Referring to the pyramid of brand resonance from Keller [16], the peak of engagement or loyalty to a brand is active engagement i.e. when consumers are willing to devote their thoughts, time, and financial resources to help develop the brand. So, although GA's engagement with the GenRe program has entered the resonance stage, it has not yet reached its highest peak. Of course, it is understandable considering GA is a student who does not have an income.

The study of Inayat & Khan (2021) regarding job satisfaction and its effect on employee's performance found that satisfied employee were comparatively more productive, spent their personal resources in a more effective and constructive manner than dissatisfied employees. Moreover, satisfied employees have the ability to initiate new ways, ideas, and programs in order to achieve organizational goals successfully [33]. It would be unfortunate if GA's dissatisfaction eventually impacted their effectiveness as change agents, which had thus far been well-executed. The BKKBN as the initiator of this program, should optimize the management of GA as a change agent that influences the success of GenRe.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Keller's [16] brand resonance pyramid, which is typically employed to describe customer loyalty to a commercial brand, can be utilized to comprehend the stages of engagement between GA and their position as a change agent for the GenRe initiative. GA, who was originally a potential target audience for adopting the values promoted by GenRe, i.e. avoiding pre-marital sex, early marriage, and drug use, can gradually increase their engagement with GenRe. Beginning with being the target audience, then became community members, and finally GA. GA attained the highest resonance peak, indicating that it was pleased with its performance as a change agent. Due to GA's financial limits, this facet of satisfaction did not attain active participation upon closer inspection.

Future research should emphasize the impact of change agents' satisfaction with their responsibilities on their performance. Other approaches to branding, such as brand association, brand image and brand engagement, may be utilized in the investigation of this issue in order to ascertain the change agent's view of the organization.

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